

MASTER SN CURVE APPROACH- A HYBRID MULTISCALE APPROACH TO FATIGUE SIMULATION OF SHORT FIBER COMPOSITES

Atul Jain*,^{1,2}, Yasmine Abdin², Stefan Straesser¹, Wim Van Paepegem³, Ignaas Verpoest², Stepan V. Lomov²

¹ Siemens Industry Software NV,
Interleuvenlaan 68, B-3001 Leuven, Belgium
Email: atul.jain@siemens.com/stefan.straesser@siemens.com

²Department of Materials Engineering, KU Leuven
Kasteelpark Arenberg 44, B-3001 Leuven, Belgium
Email: Stepan.Lomov@mtm.kuleuven.be

³Department of Material Science and Engineering
Ghent University, Belgium
Email: Wim.VanPaepegem@ugent.be

Keywords: Short fiber composite, fatigue, damage, multi-scale analysis

ABSTRACT

Typical short fiber reinforced composites (SFRC) components have a different local statistical distribution of fiber orientation leading to different mechanical and fatigue behavior at different points. For a component-sized calculation, each element in the FE model is modelled as a Representative Volume Element (RVE). Unlike for static properties, there are no analytical methods to estimate the SN curve of a RVE. As a result one usually has to rely on expensive, time consuming and difficult to perform test-based interpolation methods. To overcome this problem we developed a hybrid multi-scale method to predict the local SN curves of SFRC; this proposed method involves both multiscale-mechanics and tests.

The key assumption behind this scheme is that for SFRC the damage development and consequent stiffness degradation during cyclic loading with different orientation distributions are similar. Damage operator which represents the loss of stiffness due to different damage events is calculated for the first cycle of loading. Validated models were developed within the framework of the Mori-Tanaka formulation to model fiber matrix debonding and matrix non-linearity; the damage parameter is calculated based on loss of stiffness due to fiber matrix debonding. The proposed models are validated with experiments.

Next for the validation of the assumptions, the loss of stiffness curves were extracted for each of the data points and a statistical comparison of the curves is performed for the data points which have similar lifetime to failure. A method to compare the loss of stiffness by characterizing the curves and then performing an ANOVA analysis using Fisher criteria is developed. It was proven that for similar life to failure, the variation in loss of stiffness curves for SFRC with different orientation is not statistically significant.

1 INTRODUCTION

Increasingly SFRC are being looked at as possible replacements for metals in semi-structural applications in automobiles. This is due to the rising awareness and regulations towards reducing CO₂ emissions. Lack of proper methods for fatigue simulation has often been seen as a bottleneck for large scale deployment of SFRC in industrial use. SFRC are usually manufactured by the injection molding process and have a different local statistical distribution of fiber orientation at every point. Fatigue properties of SFRC are known to depend on the fiber orientation distribution (FOD) and fiber length distribution (FLD) of the fibers [1-3], but the exact relationship is unknown. This is because unlike

static properties which are well understood, the understanding of the fatigue behavior of composites in general is still rather limited.

For a component-level simulation, each point in the FE model has a known statistical distribution of length and orientation of fibers which is often predicted using manufacturing simulation tools. Each point in the FE mesh can therefore be imagined as a different material whose static and fatigue properties need to be estimated. A schematic representation of the component level simulation of SFRC is shown in **Figure 1** *Error! Reference source not found.*

Figure 1: A simplistic schematic representation of fatigue simulation process of SFRC

Starting from the mold geometry, a manufacturing simulation of injection molding is usually performed to calculate the 2nd order orientation tensor at every point. This data is then transferred to homogenization software which calculates the effective stiffness at that point. The effective properties at every point must then be transferred to the FE and fatigue solver. A mapping tool ensures that the mesh of the manufacturing simulation software is mapped appropriately to the FE and fatigue solver. Apart from the stiffness of the RVE, the SN curve must also be calculated; this aspect of the component level simulation is studied in this paper.

For an RVE, one can calculate the effective static properties of the composite by a number of different methods, for example the Mori-Tanaka (MT) formulation [4]. However, unlike elasticity there are no well understood and universally accepted formulations to describe fatigue, thus there is an absence of an analytical method to predict the SN curve of a composite material. This paper is an attempt to estimate the local SN curves of a SFRC component based on only one SN curve as input.

The standard practice in fatigue simulation of SFRC is to make simplifying assumptions about the orientation and the length distribution of the fibers and use test-based interpolation methods. Such methods depend on a number of tests on coupons with extreme FOD [5]. Furthermore, since it is almost impossible to create test coupons with perfect extreme alignment some extrapolation might be needed as well. Other approaches include use of empirical reduction factors for different factors like FOD, length, notch, mean stress etc. such an approach is often used for polymers [6]. A similar approach which requires extremely large number of tests and lacks physical basis was tried by Guster et al. [7] and Mosenbacher et al. [8] for the simulation of SFRC.

Another practical approach is to normalize the fatigue strength based on the ultimate tensile strength (UTS). This approach is based on experiments that showed the proportionality of both properties [1-3, 9, 10]. Such an approach has two major limitations, first there is no physical reasoning as to why the fatigue strengths must vary in the same manner as the tensile strength, there are experimental evidences which confirm that the failure mechanisms for damage propagation and final failure are different during tensile and fatigue loading [10-12]. The phenomena near final failure (catastrophic loss of load-carrying ability) during tensile failure are different from the phenomena during “slow” loss of load-carrying ability during cyclic loading. And secondly to be able to use this method one has to either model tensile strengths of SFRC or experimentally derive the UTS for every orientation. There are no known reliable methods to predict the tensile strength of SFRC accurately.

There are some studies which are based on a fracture mechanics approach have been tried with varying degrees of success [3, 13, 14]. Apart from a SN curve, the input for such an approach is a fatigue crack growth parameter. Experimental tests to derive the fatigue crack growth parameter are

quite complicated. Damage leads to energy dissipation and energy dissipation leads to increase in heat generation. Based on this principle, Meneghetti et al. [15] and Jegou et al. [16] proposed a method for SN curve prediction of SFRC based on the specific heat dissipation, such an approach requires rather extensive and difficult tests.

Thus one can conclude that there are a number of methods to estimate the local SN curve of a SFRC component. However, all of them depend on a number of input parameters and also sometimes lack physical basis.

This paper aims to relate the damage at the microscopic level to the macroscopic fatigue properties and propose a hybrid multi-scale approach – the Master SN curve approach. The key innovative idea in this process is that it combines test results and simulation results (hybrid approach) on different scales (microscopic simulation, macroscopic fatigue behavior), overcoming problems of depending on too many expensive tests (pure test-based macroscopic approach) and efficiency (pure microscopic simulation approach).

Section 2 of this paper describes the formulation of the Master SN curve approach (MSNC). Section 3 is devoted to the description of the experiments and the numerical implementation. The results are shown in section 4 and the conclusions are derived in section 5.

2 FORMULATION OF THE MASTER SN CURVE APPROACH

As described in the previous section, a common method of scaling the SN curve on the basis of the UTS has some limitations. Another possible approach could be to scale the SN curve based on the endurance strength of SFRC. However estimating the endurance strength of polymer composites is not an easy task. This is because unlike metals, a single crack does not propagate to cause failure during cyclic loading. The stress values at the onset of damage is typically lower than the expected endurance strength [17]. It is known that the first mode of damage in SFRC is fiber matrix debonding. There are multiple methods to calculate the onset of debonding, for example the Modified Coulomb criteria [18]. It can be shown that the stress at which onset of debonding occurs is much lower than the expected stress to failure for a SFRC after a million cycles of loading. This is consistent with reported findings for long glass and carbon fiber composites [17]. Like all composite materials, fatigue failure of SFRC generally occurs when cracks propagate sufficiently enough to cause final failure. Under uniform cyclic loading, single fiber matrix debond cannot propagate sufficiently to cause failure of SFRC. Extent of damage in SFRC must be sufficiently big to propagate and cause final failure.

In the proposed MSNC approach the extent of damage is quantified as the loss of stiffness in the applied loading direction. It is then assumed that for SFRC with different FOD and FLD but same constituents (fiber and matrix), the extent of damage needed to propagate and cause final failure during uniform cyclic loading must be similar. In other words, it is assumed that the damage propagation (and subsequent loss of stiffness) during cyclic loading in SFRC is similar for the same number of cycles to failure.

It is known that RVE's with different FOD and different FLD have a different stress to failure for a certain number of cycles. But the stiffness degradation curve must be similar. This is the key assumption of the MSNC approach.

There are indications that this assumption is reasonable and was confirmed by De Monte et al. [2]. A thorough statistical treatment of the loss of stiffness curves is not present in literature. This must be performed for the full validation of this hypothesis.

In the proposed MSNC approach, the first cycle of loading is modelled by using the full MT formulation, this approach is chosen based on the superior predictive abilities of stresses in individual inclusions [19]. Onset, progression of fiber matrix debonding and subsequent loss of stiffness is based on the concept of “equivalent bonded inclusions”–*EqBI* in short. A thorough mathematical treatment of the EqBI concept has been presented in [18, 20]. Matrix non-linearity is accounted for by a secant modulus approach [21].

The damage parameter which is based on the loss of stiffness is calculated. The damage parameter is defined by the following relation:

$$E_1 = E_0(1 - d) \quad (1)$$

where, E_1 is the Young's modulus of the RVE in the axial direction after first half cycle of load, while E_0 is the initial Young's modulus and d is the value of the damage parameter. This proposed idea of scaling of SN-curve is based on the damage parameter that represents the loss of stiffness in the loading direction due to damage in the first cycle. A schematic representation of the proposed scheme is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2 A schematic representation of the MSNC approach

Each data point in the SN curve gives information about number of cycles to failure (abscissa) and the strength to failure for the number of cycles (ordinate). Based on the reference SN curve, the values of the damage parameter are calculated for the ordinate points corresponding to different values of abscissa. It is then assumed that for a given abscissa, different RVE may have different ordinates, but the damage parameter values corresponding to the abscissa are the same. Thus for different RVE's, for a given abscissa, the ordinate is estimated by calculating the stress levels required to attain the same value of the damage parameter as was calculated from the input SN curve. Using this principle, the points in the SN curves of different RVE can be estimated.

3 MATERIALS AND TESTS

3.1 Material and experimental set up

To create coupons for the tensile and fatigue tests, polybutylene terephthalate (PBT) reinforced with 50% weight fraction of glass fiber (equivalent volume fraction is 0.35) compound was injection molded to plates having dimensions 170×170×2 mm. Coupons were machined from the plates in three directions, inclined at angles $\Phi = 0, 45$ and 90 with respect to the prevailing flow direction. For the rest of the paper, they are referred to as 0, 45 and 90 degree coupon respectively. The Young's modulus for the glass fiber and the matrix was given to be 72 and 2.6 GPa respectively while the Poisson's ratio is 0.22 and 0.37, while the strength of the matrix is taken to be 55 MPa [22].

Manufacturing simulation was performed to calculate the fiber orientation distribution of the coupons. Manufacturing simulation was done by the manufacturing simulation software SIGMASOFT [23]. Particular attention was paid to the region comprising the gauge length of the coupon. Simulation results showed that there was very little variation of the 2nd order orientation tensor in the gauge length of the coupon. This implies that the orientation distribution of inclusions is uniform throughout the gauge length of the coupons. For numerical simulation the entire coupon could be treated as a single RVE, whose orientation distribution of inclusions is described by the second order orientation tensor predicted by the manufacturing simulation. The orientation tensor of the 0-degree coupon was found to be

$$a_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.81 & 0.018 & 0.137 \\ 0.018 & 0.11 & 0.004 \\ 0.137 & 0.004 & 0.079 \end{bmatrix}$$

The orientation tensor of the 45 and 90-degree coupons were calculated by rotating of the 0° orientation tensor. The aspect ratio of the fibers is taken to be constant and equal to 20.

Fatigue tests were performed using a hydraulic horizontal Schenck fatigue testing machine for the 0, 45 and 90-degree coupons. The machine was equipped with a load cell of 10 kN. Tests were load controlled and a sinusoidal load function with constant amplitude was applied. The applied loads had an r-ratio of 0.1. Applied stresses were calculated dividing the applied load by the specimen net area, while the criterion to end the fatigue tests was complete specimen separation into two or more parts or no breakage until 10⁶ cycles. The tests were performed at a load frequency of 10Hz; this was chosen such that the temperature measured on the specimen surface did not exceed the test temperature by more than 5°C. Temperature monitoring was operated by a film type NiCr–Ni thermocouple, clamped on the central part of the specimen surface. It was noticed that the rise of temperature in the surface of the specimen increases as the frequency of the applied load was increased and was about 3.3°C at 10Hz; it was decided not to go for higher frequencies to avoid resonance frequency problems with the machine. An extensometer was mounted on the specimens during the cyclic loading to keep track of the loss of stiffness during cyclic loading. Tensile tests were performed on the specimens which survived a million cycles of loading as well as on the virgin samples and the difference in their behavior was compared.

3.2 Numerical implementation of the MSNC

A virtual realization of the RVE was created for each of the 0, 45 and 90 degree specimens. The input is the 2nd order orientation tensor, an RVE of 2000 inclusions is created based on the method of Onat and Leckie [24]. The first cycle of loading is modelled within the framework of the MT formulation. Non-linear stress strain behavior of the SFRC is simulated by modelling fiber matrix debonding as described in [18] and by modelling matrix non-linearity using the secant modulus approach.

One SN curve at a time is taken as the reference SN curve and the other two SN curves are predicted and compared with the experimental results. The validation is repeated for the three SN curves. The validation of the proposed MSNC approach is performed at three different numbers of cycles to failures: 10⁴, 10⁵ and 10⁶ cycles.

3.3 Comparisons of the loss of stiffness curves

Loss of stiffness is calculated for each point in the SN curve by correlating the stress and strain for every cycle in a linear fit. The slope of the fitted line is taken to be the secant modulus of the test coupon for a particular cycle.

It is known that the loss of stiffness varies non-linearly with increasing number of cycles. However when plotted in a log-log plot the loss of stiffness curve is usually seen to be close to linear. The loss of stiffness curves are fitted to a power equation for each test.

$$E_N = E_o N^\alpha \quad (2)$$

where, E_N is the stiffness after N number of cycles, E_o is the initial stiffness and α is a fit parameter. Taking logarithm on both sides, one gets

$$\log(E_N) = \log(E_o) + \alpha \log N \quad (3)$$

In a log-log plot, this equation corresponds to a straight line with form, $y = mx+c$; where m is the slope and c is the intercept.

Similar to the K-ratio of the SN curve, the K-ratio of the loss of stiffness curve is defined as follows:

$$K - ratio = -1/\alpha \tag{4}$$

For each test variant it is ensured that there was at least 3-4 data points with similar number of cycles to failure. The values of the k-ratio and the intercept are used to perform an analysis of variance (ANOVA). This will ascertain whether the variance of the slope (and the intercept) within one variant is statistically different from other types of coupons.

Three steps are performed for a statistical comparison of the curves

- 1 The curves are fit to the power equation and the residual fit of the regression fit parameter is compared to ensure that the curves fit similarly to the power equation. This is a necessary step before ANOVA can be performed.
- 2 The k-ratio of the curve is compared and ANOVA analysis is performed. ANOVA analysis compares the variance in a group with the variance in other group and can tell whether or not the variances are statistically significant depending on the condition:

$$Fisher-statistic F < F_{crit} \tag{5}$$

Fisher-statistic F is an indicator of the variance in the different sets of data and F_{crit} is a value which depends on the size of the data set and prescribed significance level [25]. For the calculations a 95% significance is tested.

- 3 The intercepts are also compared in a similar manner for a significance level of 95%.

Therefore the hypothesis of the similarity of the different loss of stiffness curves is tested for a composite hypothesis of 90.25% (95*95 %)significance. Microsoft Excel based add-ins were used for the statistical analysis.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Experiment results

The results of the fatigue tests are presented in **Figure 3**. It is seen that the strength of SFRC decreases as the orientation of the coupon increased. However this increase is not linear; the observed strength of the 45 degree coupon is only slightly higher than the strength of the 90 degree coupon and not equal to the mean of the strengths of the 0 and 90 degree coupons.

Figure 3 SN curve of 50% Glass Fiber reinforced PBT, coupons are machined from injection molded plates at an angle of 0, 45 and 90 degree with respect to the flow direction of the matrix. Dotted lines indicate 90% confidence interval limits. Hollow markers indicate runouts.

4.2 MSNC approach

The simulated results of the MSNC approach are shown in Figure 4. The experimental SN curve is denoted by solid lines and the 90 percent confidence intervals are denoted by dotted lines. Blue, red and green colors are used to depict the 0, 45 and 90 degree coupon respectively. In the figure rectangular markers indicate the predicted data points. It was observed that the predicted SN curves correlate well to the experimental SN curves for the three simulations. In each of the three cases the predicted SN points in the curve are within the 90% confidence interval. However there seems to be a gradual increase in error as the number of cycles to failure is decreased.

Figure 4 Predictions of the MSNC approach with one of the curves as the reference SN curve and the other two are simulated. Rectangular markers indicate the predicted data points. Material is PBT reinforced with 50% weight fraction GF, injection molded into plates and machined in different directions, R -ratio = 0.1 (a) SN curve of 0-degree coupon is taken as the reference SN curve (b) SN curve of 45-degree coupon is taken as the reference SN curve (c) SN curve of 90-degree coupon is taken as the reference SN curve

4.3 Loss of stiffness curves

The loss of stiffness curves for the 0, 45 and 90 degree coupons which survived million cycles is presented in Figure 5a. The loss of stiffness of all the 90-degree coupons could not be extracted from the fatigue data since the load cell values were not reliable. This is because a 10kN load cell was attached to the machine but the applied load was in the range of 1kN. Also, the negative slope and the intercepts are illustrated in the form of a histogram in Figure 5b, c.

Figure 5 Loss of stiffness for 0, 45 and 90 degree coupons which survived a million cycles. (a) Loss of stiffness curves, both the axes are logarithmic (b) Negative slope of the curves (c) Intercept of the curves

A qualitative analysis of the plot confirms that the loss of stiffness during cyclic loading is independent of the FOD of the coupon; this is further confirmed by a statistical analysis. For the size of the data and for the 95% significance level, the critical Fisher score, F_{crit} was found to be 4.73. The Fisher score for the variance in the negative slope and the intercept was calculated to be 1.57 and 0.71 respectively. This confirms that the loss of stiffness curves during cyclic loading are similar for the 0, 45 and 90 degree coupons and that the same curve can be used for design analysis. This is the basic hypothesis of the MSNC approach.

Depending on the number of cycles to failure, the fatigue tests were divided in three groups. The groups are chosen in such a way that there are at least 2-3 points per group for every coupon type.

The range of number of cycles to failure for the three groups is as follows:

High cycle region (group 1): 10^6 Cycles

Mid cycle region (group 2): 279940 to 20673 cycles

Low cycle region (group 3): 1261 to 8072 cycles

The results of the ANOVA analysis for the three different groups are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Critical Fisher score and Fisher score for the intercept and the negative slope

Group	Critical Fisher score	Fisher score for the intercept	Fisher score for negative slope
Group 1	4.73	1.57	0.71
Group 2	4.25	0.63	0.35
Group 3	3.98	1.27	2.41

It was observed that the Fisher score is less than the critical Fisher score for the three groups of data. For group 3, data corresponding to low cycle data, the Fisher score is found to be very close to the critical Fisher score. This implies that the variance in the loss of stiffness curves becomes more statistically significant for low cycle region. However in each of the three cases it was confirmed that the loss of stiffness are statistically insignificant for a significance level of 90% and the assumptions of the MSNC approach stand validated.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A novel hybrid multi-scale method to predict the local SN curves was developed and implemented. The predictions of the MSNC approach and the critical assumptions were validated with experimental data. It was seen that the predictions of the MSNC approach are in good agreement with the experimental values. It was observed that the error in the predictions of the MSNC increases when the input number of cycles was taken to be 10^4 .

The fact that limited test data is required could be a breakthrough in view of further industrial deployment of composites solutions in industry; since collection of fatigue data is often seen as a major bottleneck for industrial deployment. The proposed method has been implemented in industrial software LMS Virtual.Lab Durability [26] part of Siemens PLM software [27].

A systematic method for analyzing the loss of stiffness curves was developed and used to compare the loss of stiffness for different coupons. It is seen that there can be different loss of stiffness curves for coupons with the same FOD, similar applied load and similar number of cycles to failure. However, the variance in the different loss of stiffness curves during tests with similar number of cycles to failure is independent of the FOD.

The MSNC approach can also be used to predict the SN curve of a RVE when subjected to a certain uni-axial load. This opens interesting possibilities for extensions to multi-axial loads, this aspect of the MSNC approach is the scope of future research activity.

6 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank the IWT Vlaanderen for funding this research as a part of the project "Fatigue life prediction of random fiber composites using hybrid multi-scale modelling methods" - COMPFAT Baekeland mandate number 100689. We also want to thank PART Engineering GmbH for opening suitable interfaces in their software Converse to facilitate the analysis presented in this paper. Thanks also to Christophe Liefoghe and Dr. Michael Hack from Siemens Industry Software NV for useful discussions and constructive feedback. I. Verpoest is holder of the Toray Chair in Composites at KULeuven.

7 REFERENCES

1. Bernasconi, A., et al., *Effect of fibre orientation on the fatigue behaviour of a short glass fibre reinforced polyamide-6*. International Journal of Fatigue, 2007. **29**(2): p. 199-208.
2. De Monte, M., E. Moosbrugger, and M. Quaresimin, *Influence of temperature and thickness on the off-axis behaviour of short glass fibre reinforced polyamide 6.6 cyclic loading*. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2012. **41**(10): p. 1368-1379.
3. Klimkeit, B., et al. *Multiaxial fatigue behavior of short-fiber reinforced thermoplastic roof bars*. in *ICMFF9*. 2013.
4. Mori, T. and K. Tanaka, *Average stress in matrix and average elastic energy of materials with misfitting inclusions*. Acta Metallurgica, 1973. **21**(5): p. 571-574.
5. Vervoort, S., *Fatigue Analysis of polymer components with short fiber reinforcements*, in *NAFEMS World Congress*. 2013: Salzburg, Austria.
6. Erhard, G., *Designing with polymers*. 1999: Carl Hanser Publishing, Munich/Vienna.

7. Guster, C., et al., *Evaluation of a Simulation Process for Fatigue Life Calculation of Short Fibre Reinforced Plastic Components*. 11th International Conference on the Mechanical Behavior of Materials (Icm11), 2011. **10**: p. 6.
8. Mosenbacher, A., et al., *Modelling and validation of fatigue life calculation method for short fiber reinforced injection molded parts*, in *16th European conference of composite materials*. 2014: Sevilla, Spain.
9. Bernasconi, A., et al., *Effect of reprocessing on the fatigue strength of a fibreglass reinforced polyamide*. *Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 2007. **38**(3): p. 710-718.
10. Zago, A. and G.S. Springer, *Fatigue lives of short fiber reinforced thermoplastics parts*. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, 2001. **20**(7): p. 606-620.
11. Arif, M.F., et al., *Multiscale fatigue damage characterization in short glass fiber reinforced polyamide-66*. *Composites Part B-Engineering*, 2014. **61**: p. 55-65.
12. Horst, J.J. and J.L. Spoormaker, *Mechanisms of fatigue in short glass fiber reinforced polyamide 6*. *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 1996. **36**(22): p. 2718-2726.
13. Klimkeit, B., et al., *Multiaxial fatigue life assessment for reinforced polymers*. *International Journal of Fatigue*, 2011. **33**(6): p. 766-780.
14. Wyzgoski, M.G. and G.E. Novak, *Predicting fatigue S-N (stress-number of cycles to fail) behavior of reinforced plastics using fracture mechanics theory*. *Journal of Materials Science*, 2005. **40**(2): p. 295-308.
15. Meneghetti, G. and M. Quaresimin, *Fatigue strength assessment of a short fiber composite based on the specific heat dissipation*. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 2010. **42**(2): p. 217-225.
16. Jegou, L., et al., *Fast prediction of the Wohler curve from heat build-up measurements on Short Fiber Reinforced Plastic*. *International Journal of Fatigue*, 2013. **47**: p. 259-267.
17. Lomov, S.V., V. Carvelli, and I. Verpoest. *Correlations between damage initiation thresholds in textile composites and fatigue life limits*. in *The Proceedings of the 10th international conference on textile composites: recent advances in textile composites*. 2010.
18. Jain, A., et al., *Effective anisotropic properties of inclusions with imperfect interface for Eshelby-based models*. Submitted to *Composite Structures*.
19. Jain, A., et al., *Pseudo-Grain Discretization And Full Mori Tanaka Formulation For Random Heterogeneous Media: Predictive Abilities For Stresses In Individual Inclusions And The Matrix*. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2013. **87**: p. 86-93.
20. Jain, A., et al. *Model for partially debonded inclusions in the framework of mean-field homogenization*. in *11th TEXCOMP*. 2013. Leuven, Belgium.
21. Tandon, G.P. and G.J. Weng, *A theory of particle-reinforced plasticity*. *Journal of Applied Mechanics-Transactions of the Asme*, 1988. **55**(1): p. 126-135.
22. PLASTICS, C., *CAMPUS® - a material information system for the plastics industry*, <http://www.campusplastics.com/>, Editor. 2014.
23. Sigmasoft, *SIGMA Engineering GmbH, Aachen*, in <http://www.sigmasoft.de/>. 2014.
24. Onat, E.T. and F.A. Leckie, *Representation of mechanical behavior in the presence of change internal structure*. *Transactions of the ASME. Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 1988. **55**(1): p. 1-10.
25. Fisher, R.A. and F. Yates, *Statistical tables for biological, agricultural and medical research*. *Statistical tables for biological, agricultural and medical research.*, 1949(Ed. 3.).

26. *LMS Virtual.Lab Durability-Durability analysis for optimal product performance*, http://www.plm.automation.siemens.com/en_us/products/lms/virtual-lab/durability/, Editor. 2014.
27. *Siemens PLM software*. www.siemens.com/plm 2014